

Improving machining efficiency by machine system intelligence

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Abstract

Digitalization and the implementation and application of sensor integrated 'intelligent' tools, fixtures and machine tool components provide a huge potential regarding the optimization of manufacturing systems in terms of productivity, quality, flexibility, reliability and availability as well as economic viability. Moreover, these approaches can essentially contribute to a reduction of energy and resource consumption and, thus, to an improved efficiency with respect to the environmental impact of production. This publication presents some exemplary technologies and discusses their potential regarding a reduction of the CO₂ footprint in manufacturing.

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1 Introduction

With the aim to overcome current challenges such as raising production cost in high-wage countries and increasing skilled labor shortage, and in order to improve manufacturing flexibility, availability and efficiency, more and more industrial developments as well as scientific research are focused on automation solutions, digitization, specific implementation of machine learning and the integration of 'system intelligence' up to autonomous functionality and self-optimizing machining systems [1]. Modern communication technology, control interfaces and sensor integrated devices such as tools and machine components enable interconnected manufacturing environments with distributed multi-physical data acquisition, information processing and adaptive optimization control loops [2,3]. In order to elaborate suitable solutions of digitalized production systems and factories, sophisticated laboratories, development and test facilities were established recently, as for example the 'DigiLab' at the Institute for Machine Tools (IfW) at the University of Stuttgart (Fig. 1). In view of the climate change and considering the reduction of energy and resource consumption in production as a requirement of utmost importance, the target of optimization must include not only productivity, quality and economic viability but also transparency regarding the environmental impact and the minimization of the carbon footprint of manufacturing. Against this background, this paper provides an overview of exemplary 'intelligent systems' for machining and highlights the related environmental effects by an analysis of CO₂-equivalents. As can be seen by the presented solutions and findings, innovations in the field of manufacturing equipment and machine tools can contribute to a higher efficiency of production also with respect to environmental aspects.

Figure 1: IfW – “DigiLab” for digital solutions in manufacturing (research, development and education).

2 Sensitive clamping of thin-walled workpieces

Lightweight design and the reduction of material usage in components and products by means of structural optimization lead to thin-walled workpieces that have to be machined with appropriate manufacturing machines and equipment. Thin-walled workpieces tend to vibrations in machining operations and they are prone to distortions due to residual stresses which are released and induced by the material removal [4]. Moreover, sensitive workpiece clamping is necessary in order to on the one hand avoid mechanical loads that deform the part but, on the other hand, to ensure stable and robust fixation even bearing process forces and gravitational or inertial influences. For this purpose, a sensory chuck jaw was developed at the IfW (Fig. 2) [5].

Figure 2: Sensory chuck jaw for turning applications.

This sensory clamping element allows for a direct measurement of clamping forces that act on the workpiece during the machining processes. In the case of thin-walled parts, these clamping forces can provoke workpiece deformations and, thus, affect the final accuracy of the part. As the stiffness of the workpiece decreases with progressing material removal, deformations and deviations from the desired shape increase and the stability of the clamping can fall below a critical state. The sensory jaw enables a sensitive monitoring and adjustment of clamping forces, and, by this, contributes to an improved capability and performance in machining thin-walled lightweight parts.

3 Semi-active lightweight high-performance tool

In order to significantly reduce the mass of an exemplary industrial high-performance milling tool but to improve its machining performance at the same time, an innovative semi-actively damped tool structure incorporating a hybrid material combination was realized at the IfW (Fig. 3) [6]. The tool with a diameter of 100 mm, a length of 320 mm and 44 cutting inserts consists of a topology optimized hollow steel body with particle dampers, an internal CFRP tube and an adjustable magneto-rheologic fluid (MRF) damper. Compared with the industrial tool, a mass reduction by 36% is achieved. Due to the improved dynamic properties, the material removal rate in milling steel 1.057 (AISI 1024) can be increased by a factor of eight and the surface roughness of the machined part can be reduced drastically at the same time. In order to allow an adjustment of the MRF damper to the actual process conditions and tool temperature states, a multi-sensor system and data processing and communication electronics are integrated into the tool. The multi-sensor system comprises temperature, acceleration, force and acoustic emission (AE) measuring functionality.

Figure 3: Lightweight high performance milling tool with integrated multi-sensor system.

Figure 4: Comparison of CO₂ emissions.

Regarding the improved performance and functionality of the innovative lightweight tool (LWT) an interesting question is, whether also an improved efficiency with respect to the overall CO₂ emission could be achieved. In order to answer this question, the new tool system is compared with the conventional reference tool by means of a balancing of CO₂ equivalents. For this, the manufacturing routes of both tools, the origin or fabrication (E_H) and delivery (E_T) of the materials as well as the emissions during the use phase (E_B) and those caused by recycling (E_R) are considered. Figure 4 shows a summary of the elaborated results. As can be seen, the newly developed system (LWT) shows a significantly improved efficiency compared to the conventional reference (Ref) tool.

4 Pre-stressed carbon-fiber reinforced polymer concrete in machine structures

Polymer concrete (also known as mineral cast) provides advantageous material properties with respect to damping (i.e. dynamic stiffness) and thermal stability compared to metal structures in machine tool elements [7]. Due to its lower density, in principle, even a lightweight design capability exists. However, because of its limited tensile strength, polymer concrete is hardly applied for moved machine components such as slides or traveling columns. The material is predominantly used in stationary machine beds and structures with more or less cubic geometries and shapes. In order to overcome the limitations of the tensile strength, pre-stressed carbon-fiber reinforced polymer concrete is investigated as a new class of materials for machine tool structures at the IfW [8,9] (Fig. 5). As visible in Fig. 5d, a significantly higher breaking load compared to pure polymer concrete can be achieved. This allows the realization of topology optimized components (Fig. 5a-c). Furthermore, sensory systems can easily be integrated into these structures during casting to realize ‘feeling’ components.

Figure 5: Pre-stressed carbon fiber reinforced polymer concrete for applications in machine tool structures.

Also for these developments, investigations regarding the CO₂ footprint were carried out [10]. Subject to the mass of integrated carbon fibers, and depending on the origin of the considered materials, advantageous CO₂ equivalents could be identified (Fig. 6), whereas the effects of the mass reduction and functional integration during the use phase could not be analyzed up to now.

Figure 6: Comparison of CO₂ equivalents.

5 Summary and outlook

This paper presents exemplary ‘intelligent systems’ for manufacturing applications and discusses their specific impact on the efficiency in production. In this regard, not only productivity, manufacturing quality and economic viability are considered, but also environmental aspects such as the CO₂ footprint are incorporated. It is shown that by means of innovative solutions, improved capability in terms of the production of lightweight products and the reduction of energy and resource consumption can be achieved. Furthermore, the presented investigations reveal, that decreased CO₂ equivalents can be gained. In future work, the environmental impact of innovative approaches will increasingly be incorporated in global optimization procedures. Though fundamental balancing methods are already available, further work is necessary in order to provide the necessary calculation schemes and data platforms.

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7 References

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